

Table 10: How Text Segments (codes) Were Mapped

1 st Order Representative Codes (Quotes From Data)	Related Logics / Themes	How Logics Conflict / Rationale for Coding
<p><i>“Really being able to build relationships with, and wrap your head around 250 clients, yeah, in general, it’s for one person, I don’t think it’s feasible.”</i></p>	<p>Fiduciary Logics</p> <p>Service Logics</p> <p>Sales Logics</p> <p>Wellbeing (theme)</p>	<p>Having too many clients creates stress for the advisor, which impacts the advisor's wellbeing.</p> <p>It impacts the proper exercise of fiduciary duty and the degree to which an adequate level of service can be provided, which impacts the client's financial wellbeing.</p>
<p><i>“If you are giving the FCs the impression that you don’t have that capacity, then you aren’t going to reach your NSF target.¹”</i></p>	<p>Sales Logics</p> <p>Fiduciary Logics</p>	<p>FCs must be confident that the PCA has the capacity to handle new and existing clients, or they will cease making referrals to them. However, regardless of capacity, PCAs must accept new referrals to hit their targets. Having too many clients strains the ability of PCAs to provide each client with adequate attention to fulfill their fiduciary duty.</p>
<p><i>“As we say, are we what we say we are? Which is wealth managers. Because I think we were talking out of both sides of our mouth. I think we, we’re marketing ourselves as wealth managers, but all of our energy was focused on sales. So, to me that was, that was a huge pit in my stomach. And it just, I just thought it was incongruent with all the marketing and you know, how we position Private Client to prospects, right?”</i></p>	<p>Sales Logics</p> <p>Service Logics</p> <p>Fiduciary Logics</p> <p>Wellbeing (theme)</p>	<p>This quote highlights the tension between Sales Logics and Service Logics with implications for tensions between Sales Logics and Fiduciary Logics (‘incongruent’) and implications for advisor wellbeing (pit of my stomach).</p>

¹ NSF refers to a type of sales target.